

ANALYSIS OF CONE PENETROMETER LIQUID LIMIT FLOW CURVE USING MATHEMATICAL MODEL (MODEL 1)

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a mathematical model which defines the moisture-penetration relationship using British cone. The developed mathematical model gives a unique opportunity of computing or predicting the cone penetration of the soil even at a very low moisture content at which, due to practical limitation it is impossible to determine the soil penetration. The model was found to fit the moisture-penetration data reasonably well. The model was used to compute the penetration of soil at the plastic limit of 394 soils. This study indicates that the plastic limit cannot be defined using one unique penetration value.

KEYWORDS: plastic limit; liquid limit; plasticity index; shear strength

INTRODUCTION

There are two main methods of determining liquid limit. These are fall cone (BS 1377: Part 2: 1990) and the Casagrande/percussion method (BS 1377: Part 2: 1990 and AASHTO T89-2002). The fall cone method is termed as the preferred method in BS 1377: Part 2: 1990 because the test results are more reproducible, and it is easier to perform. AASHTO T89-2002 is still retaining the Casagrande method as the principal method of determining the liquid limit. In accordance with BS 1377: Part 2:1990, the liquid limit is taken as the moisture content, which gives 20 mm penetration with standardised cone.

The plastic limit is defined as the moisture content at which the soil changes from semi-solid to a plastic state. According to BS 1377: Part 2:1990 and AASHTO T90-2000, the plastic limit is determined by rolling a soil ball into a thread of 3 mm ($1/8^{\text{th}}$ of an inch) in five to ten

complete forward and back movements (sometimes up to 15 for heavy clays) until the thread shears both longitudinally and transversely (crumbles). The moisture content, at which the soil thread crumbles is determined and taken as the plastic limit.

In accordance with BS 1377: Part 2:1990, the liquid limit fall cone flow curve is modelled as linear on a natural scale within the penetration range of about 20 ± 5 mm. However, this study indicates that this linear moisture-penetration is valid within this narrow range of moisture-penetration relationship of 20 ± 5 mm. Outside this range, the moisture-penetration relationship is not linear. The studies carried by Kaumoto and Houlsby (2001), Feng (2001) and Sharma and Bora (2003) indicate that the cone penetration-moisture data can be modelled using *log-log* models within the penetration range of 26 – 3 mm. Based on an earlier suggestion made by Skempton and Northey (1953) that the shear strength at the plastic limit is 100 fold that of liquid limit, it was suggested by these researchers that the plastic limit be taken as the moisture content which gives a penetration of 2 mm. Sridharan *et al* (1999), proposed computation of plasticity index from flow index defined as the slope of the flow curve plotted on the semi-logarithmic plot. Lee Jr *et al* (2009) proposed the use of dual weight cone and plotting the square root of penetration versus the water content and proposed to read off the penetration at the square root of 2, i.e. 1.414 mm.

BACKGROUND OF LIQUID LIMIT FALL CONE

The original method of determining the liquid limit is the percussion method developed by Casagrande (1932). Measurements of shear strength at Casagrande liquid limit was carried

by Skempton & Northey (1953), Casagrande (1958), Norman (1958), Youssef *et al* (1965), Wroth and wood (1978), Houlsby (1982), Wood (1985), Sridharan & Prakash (1998) and Zentar *et al* (2009). Their study indicated that the shear strength of soil at Casagrande liquid limit is ranging from 0.48 -2.65 kPa. Wroth and Wood(1978) suggested a shear strength value of 1.7 kPa at the liquid limit. Based on this concept of shear strength of soil at its liquid limit, detailed study of the relationship between cone penetration and soil shear strength was carried out by Hansbo (1957), and the expression given in equation (1) was proposed for computing the shear strength of the soil at any penetration depth 'd'.

$$C_u = K \frac{W}{d^2} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where 'W' is the cone weight, 'K' is the cone factor and 'd' is the penetration depth. Using fall cone and miniature vane tests, Wood (1985) established an average cone factor of 0.85 for a cone with 30°. If these values are inserted in equation 1 (British Standard Cone $m=80$, $d=20$, $g=9.81$, $k=0.85$), the shear strength of soil at liquid limit becomes 1.67 kPa which is the same value as that suggested by Wood and Wroth (1978).

LIQUID LIMIT FLOW CURVE

In accordance with BS 1377: Part 2:1990, the moisture-penetration relationship of soil during the determination of liquid limit is established within the penetration range of 20±5 mm using a standard cone weighing 80g. The procedure requires the determination of water content at a specified range of penetration. Thereafter, the linear flow curve is established by plotting the water content as abscissa against the penetration as ordinate on a natural scale. For some soils tested during this study, the linear moisture-penetration relationship holds even at lower penetration value of about 6 mm as exemplified in Figure 1 and 2. However, if the flow curve is plotted using a linear model to cover penetration at low moisture content, the penetration at a plastic limit for some soils becomes negative

(Figure 2). Therefore, the flow curve modelled in accordance with BS testing procedure does not depict the actual liquid limit flow curve at lower penetration value, i.e. penetration of less than 6 mm. This suggests that the slope of the flow curve is not constant but is gradually varying as a function of moisture content. It can be further argued that the linear moisture-penetration relationship determined within the penetration range of 20±5 mm approximates the slope of flow curve at the liquid limit.

Figure 1 ($R^2=0.9826-0.9946$) shows crushed granitic gneiss sand mixed with bentonite mixture modelled using a linear model up low penetration values of about 6 mm. It can be seen from Figure 1 that the penetration of the soil at plastic limit extrapolated from the linear model was found to be 1.213 mm, 1.26 mm, 1.84 mm and 2.23 mm for soil with 5%, 25%, 50% and 75% bentonite respectively. The average penetration at the plastic limit for the soil-bentonite mixture was found to be 1.64 mm.

The penetration at the plastic limit for the natural soil shown in Figure 2 ($R^2= 0.9766-0.9909$), was found to be 0.754 mm, -1.26 mm and 0.245 mm. The penetration of one soil was found to be negative (imaginary and nonexistent penetration) suggesting that the liquid limit flow curve cannot be modelled using the linear model up to the plastic limit. The linear model seems to be valid only within the penetration range of 20±5 mm specified for determination of liquid limit. The moisture-penetration relationship is nonlinear at lower moisture content. Therefore, a linear model is not realistically modelling the liquid limit flow curve.

In a bid to model the liquid limit flow curve realistically, an attempt has been made by several researchers to model the flow curve using linear-log, ln-ln or log-log model such that the flow curve covers a wide range of moisture – penetration relationship. Kodikara *et al* (1986) modelled the flow curve using ln-ln, Feng (2001, 2004), Sharma and Bora (2003) modelled the flow curve as log-log.

Figure 3 and 4 show the moisture-penetration relationship modelled using log-log relationship and the associated penetration at the plastic limit. Based on the achieved coefficient of determination (R^2), it can be stated that the *log-log* model is capable of depicting the moisture penetration relationship over a wide range. However, it is worth mentioning that in most cases, the double logarithmic plotting is usually able to reduce any set of data to a visually linear relationship.

Figure 1: Moisture penetration relationship for a blend of crushed sand and bentonite plotted on a linear scale

Figure 2: Moisture penetration relationship for natural soils plotted on a linear scale

Figure 3 (sand -bentonite mixture) on the log-log scale shows that the extrapolated penetration at the plastic limit is 4.82 mm, 2.97 mm, 2.955 mm and 2.93 mm. The average penetration was found to be 3.42 mm. For natural soil shown in Figure 4, the extrapolated penetration at the plastic limit was found to be 3.49 mm, 2.32 mm and 2.68 mm. The average penetration was found to be 2.83 mm

Figure 3: Moisture- penetration relationship of the soil-bentonite mixture on log-log scale ($R^2=0.978-0.9946$)

Figure 4: Moisture- penetration relationship of natural soil on a log-log scale ($R^2=0.9631-0.9965$)

LIQUID LIMIT FLOW CURVE MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The data given in Figure 1 and 2 indicates that the flow curve is almost a straight line as fitted by a linear equation with a coefficient of determination (R^2) ranging from 0.9826-0.9946 (for sand-bentonite mixture) and 0.9766-0.9909 (for natural soil) which can be considered as perfect correlation. However, if the curves are examined critically, it can be seen that the linear model can not be used to model the liquid limit flow curve at lower penetration values. Therefore, the liquid limit flow curve can be realistically modelled using a nonlinear model. To further illustrate this concept, data shown in Figure 1 and 2 were fitted using two segments piecewise linear regression model. The fitted data suggests that the slope tends to increase as the moisture content increases. The fitted moisture-penetration relationship using piecewise linear regression model is shown in Figure 5 and 6. The coefficient of determination for the two segments piecewise linear regression model ranged from 0.996-0.999. The penetration at the plastic limit for the sand-bentonite mixture (Figure 5) extrapolated from the bilinear curve was found to be 1.69 mm, 2.66 mm, 2.59 mm, and 3.03 mm. The average penetration at the plastic limit was found to be is 2.49 mm.

Figure 5: Moisture-penetration data fitted using two segments piecewise linear regression model (soil-bentonite mixture)

Figure 6, shows natural soil liquid limit flow curve modelled using a two segments piecewise linear model (bilinear model). The fitted model shows an excellent correlation, as evidenced by the coefficient of determination of 0.992-0.996. The penetration at the plastic limit for these soils as computed from this bilinear model was found to be 1.61 mm, 1.15 mm, and 1.40 mm. The average penetration at the plastic limit for these soils was found to be 1.39 mm.

Figure 5 and 6 suggests that the liquid limit flow curve is bilinear.

Figure 6: Moisture-penetration data fitted using two segments piecewise linear regression model (natural soils)

Based on the postulation that the slope of the liquid limit flow curve is gradually decreasing as the moisture content decreases, the mathematical model which depicts the liquid limit flow curve was formulated. The model was formulated based on the following postulations :- (a) the plasticity index is the arithmetic difference between liquid limit and plastic limit; therefore, it is hypothesised that for the soil to be non-plastic, its plastic limit must be equal to its liquid limit; thus its penetration at plastic limit will be 20 mm or close 20 mm (b) the slope of the flow curve as determined within the range of 20±5 mm approximates the slope of the curve at the liquid limit (c) for penetration beyond 40 mm, the soil is in suspension, and the shear strength

of the soil is zero. The cone adhesion is also lost. Therefore, the penetration equates to a depth of the penetration cup, which is 40 mm, and it remains constant at 40 mm regardless of an increase in moisture content.

Based on these postulations, it was established that the fall cone liquid limit flow curve could be modelled as a sigmoidal function. The sigmoidal mathematical model developed is shown in equation (2).

$$h = \frac{40}{1 + e^{\frac{-x+LL}{T}}} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where 'h' is the penetration depth at any moisture content, 'x' is the moisture content, and 'T' is the flow curve constant. Differentiating equation 2, the slope of the flow curve at any moisture content can be computed using equation 3.

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{40e^{\left(\frac{-x+LL}{T}\right)}}{\left[1 + e^{\left(\frac{-x+LL}{T}\right)}\right]^2} T \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Since the slope of fall cone flow curve which defines the straight part can be determined within a penetration range of 20±5 mm using a conventional method of determining liquid limit by modelling the flow curve in the form 'y=mx+C', it can be reasonably postulated that the determined slope of the flow curve approximates the slope of the flow curve at the liquid limit. Therefore, replacing 'x' with Liquid Limit (LL), equation (3) is reduced to equation (4).

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = m = \frac{10}{T} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Since the slope of the flow curve at the liquid limit is known, then 'T' can be easily computed using equation (4). From equation (4), it can

be seen that 'T' is constant, which depends on the slope of the liquid limit flow curve. Making 'T' as a subject in equation (4), and replacing T in equation (2), the liquid limit flow curve can be expressed in terms of two parameters only namely liquid limit and slope of the flow curve at liquid limit 'm' as shown in equation (5).

$$h = \frac{40}{1 + e^{[0.1(-x+LL)m]}} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

The accuracy of this mathematical model can be checked using the cone penetrometer flow curve results given in Figure 1 and 2, where the moisture-penetration was determined to about 6 mm. The modelled and the measured value of penetration are superimposed in Figure 7 (soil-bentonite mixture) and 8 (natural soils).

The penetrations at the plastic limit for sand-bentonite mixture shown in Figure 7 was found to be 5.852 mm, 3.452 mm, 3.87 mm, and 4.49 mm, with an average penetration of 4.416 mm.

The penetrations at the plastic limit for natural soils shown in Figure 8 were found to be 3.28 mm, 2.8189 mm and 3.94 mm with an average penetration at the plastic limit of 3.34 mm.

Figure 7: The measure versus modelled penetration -moisture relationship for the soil-bentonite mixture

Figures 7 and 8 show that the proposed liquid limit flow curve mathematical model can

reasonably predict the moisture-penetration relationship reasonably well.

Figure 8: The measured versus modelled penetration- moisture relationship for natural soils

PENETRATION AT PLASTIC LIMIT

Based on the premise that the soil at plastic limit has a shear strength of 100-fold that of liquid limit, it has been suggested by several authors to redefine the plastic limit such that the plastic limit can be extrapolated from fall cone flow curve. In accordance with British Standard, the shear strength of soil at its plastic limit is estimated to be 167 kPa using the cone factor of 0.85. If this value of shear strength is inserted in equation 1, the penetration of soil at its plastic limit becomes 2 mm. However, in practice, it is difficult to achieve such low penetration such that the plastic limit can be directly read-off from the cone penetration flow curve. Based on this premise, several researchers suggested using *log-log* or linear-log plots to model the liquid limit fall cone flow curves to cover wider range of moisture-penetration relationship such that the plastic limit can be read-off directly from the flow curve at 2 mm penetration. Kodikara *et al* (1986) modelled the cone penetrometer liquid limit flow curve using *ln-ln* plot and proposed a method of determining plastic limit

from fall cone flow curve using two cones of the same geometry but different weights. The first cone is the one complying with BS 1377: Part 2: 1900 with a weight of 80g and the second cone the weight is increased to 230 g.

Based on the same premise, Feng (2001, 2004) through laboratory testing proposed the use of *log-log* model for determination of plastic limit. Feng (2001, 2004) found that the penetration at plastic limit was within the range of 1-5 mm. Sharma and Bora (2003), also based on the same premise proposed to use Swedish cone to determine plastic limit at 170 kN/m². Using the same premise, Koumoto and Houlsby (2001) proposed the use of 60°, 60 g cone to determine the plastic limit at 10 mm using log *w* - log *D* model.

The penetrations at the plastic limit of 394 soils were computed using flow curve model proposed in equation 5. The penetration data suggests that the penetration at the plastic limit is very variable, and there is no single penetration that can be used to determine the plastic limit. The penetration at the plastic limit was found to be in the range of 0.1-18 mm (for non-plastic soils, hypothetical penetration of 20 mm was computed) with an average of 7.87 mm. The penetration at the plastic limit was computed by replacing the water content 'x' with plastic limit (PL) in equation (2). The resulting equation is given as equation (6). The penetration data suggests that as the plasticity index decreases the penetration at plastic limit increases. The penetration data plotted against the plasticity index is shown in Figure 9. For most of the soil with plasticity index in the range of 20-60, the penetration at the plastic limit is within the range of 1-5mm. The same penetration range at plastic limit was reported by Feng (2001, 2004)

$$h = \frac{40}{1 + e^{[0.1(PI)m]}} \dots \dots (6)$$

Equations 2 and 5 suggest that the moisture content and the slope of the flow curve are the parameters which control the penetration as well as the shear strength of the soil.

Figure 9: Penetration at the plastic limit and Plasticity index for 394 soils

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

It has been demonstrated through this study that the conceptualised liquid limit flow curve model developed reasonably defines wide range of penetration/moisture flow curve. The model is capable of predicting soil penetration at different water content. Furthermore, it has been shown that the liquid limit flow curve is linear within a very narrow range of moisture/cone penetration. The liquid limit flow curve can be modelled using a sigmoidal or piecewise linear regression model.

This study has also demonstrated that there is no single penetration value at which the plastic limit can be defined. The penetration of the soil at the plastic limit is varying widely depending on the sensitivity of the soil to moisture content variation.

This conceptualised mathematical model of liquid limit flow curve paves the way for a

scientific method of determining the plastic limit.

References:

- Maregesi, G.R (2007)**, *development of Mathematical model for computing plastic limit from liquid limit cone penetrometer*, Msc (Highway Engineering) Dissertation, University of Dar Es Salaam
- AASHTO T89-02 (2002)** *Standard Procedure for Determining Plastic limit*, American Association of State and Transportation official.
- AASHTO T90-00 (2000)** *Procedures for Determining Liquid Limit*, American Association of State and Transportation official.
- BS 1377: Part 2: (1990)**: *Soil classification test*, British Standard Institution
- Casagrande, a (1932)**, *Research on Atterbergs Limits of soil*, Public Roads 13(8) Page 121-30 and 136.
- Feng, T (2001)**, *A linear log D- log W model for determination of consistency limits of soils*, Canadian geotechnical Journal, 38, 1335-1342.
- Feng, T (2004)**, *Using a Small Ring and Fall Cone to determine the plastic limit*, *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, America Society of Civil Engineer.
- Hansbo, S (1957)**, *A new approach to the determination of the shear strength of clay by the fall cone test*, Proc. Royal Swedish Geotechnical Institute, 14:7-47
- Houlsby, G.T (1982)**, *Theoretical Analysis of fall cone test*, *Geotechnique*, 32(2):111-118
- Kodikara, J.K, Seneviratne, HN, and Wijayakulasooriya, C.V (1986)**, *Evaluation of Plastic limit and Plasticity Index by the Cone Penetrometer*, Proc. Asian Regional Symposium on Geotechnical Problems and Practice in Foundation Engineering, National Building Research Organization, Srilanka, 1 229-233.
- Koumoto, T and Houlsby, G.T,(2001)** *Theory and practice of fall cone test*, *Geotechnique* 51, No.8, 701-712
- Sharma, B & Bora P.K, (2003)**, *Plastic limit, Liquid Limit and Un-drained Shear Strength of Soil – Reappraisal*, *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, America Society of Civil Engineer.

Skempton, A.W & Northey, R.D (1953), *The sensitivity of clays*, Geotechnique 3, NO. 1, 30-53.

Sridharan, A, Nagaraj, HB, & Prakash K, (1999), *determination of plasticity index from flow curve*, Journal of American Society of Testing Materials.

Sridharan, a.&Prakash,K. (1998), **Characteristic water contents of a fine grained soil-water system**, Geotechnique 48, No. 337-346.

Stone, K.J.L & Phan K.D, (1995), *Cone penetration tests near the plastic limit*, Geotechnique 45, No. 11 155-158.

Wood, DM (1985) *Some fall-cone tests*, Geotechnique 35(1), 282-7.

Wood, DM and Wroth, CP (1978), *The use of cone penetrometer to determine the plastic limit of soil*, Ground Engineering, 11(3):37.

Yousef, El Ramli, El Demsey (1965), *relationship between shear strength, consolidation, liquid limit and plastic limit for remolded clays*, Pro. 6th int. conf. on soil mechanics and foundation engineering, Montreal (Toronto University Press).

Zentar, R, Abriak, N.E, Dubois , V (2009), *Fall Cone Test to characterise Shear strength of Organic Sediments*, Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering, Vol. 153, No. 1, America Society of Civil Engineer